

DESIGN & ANALYSIS OF VERTICAL TAKE-OFF AND LANDING AUTONOMOUS AIR AMBULANCE AIRCRAFT

Yuvraj Pagare¹, Jaidev Reddy², Manav Patel³, Prathamesh Sapale⁴

^{1, 2, 3, 4} Department of Aerospace Engineering, Sandip University, Nashik, Maharashtra

Abstract

As we know that fixed wing unmanned aerial vehicle required long runways for take-off and landing and also flight time then other. As it is difficult to have longer runway in city area, the need of vertical take-off and landing (VTOL) arises. VTOL aircraft is the type of flight systems which have the ability to take off and land vertically, then transition to horizontal flight, and also allowing an aircraft to cover long distances at high speed and also have advantage to take-off and land in vertical manner without the need of runway. There are various applications of VTOL such as it can be used as on-demand air mobility, for cargo and package delivery, in healthcare applications, and in emergency services. The new and emerging trends of VTOL are that it can be use as air ambulance. Air Ambulance service is a board term that combines two meaning i.e. air transport with basic emergency medical services which is able to transport injured patients or sick patients to the healthcare facilities and from healthcare facilities. So, in other terms, we can say that it is basically like airlifting patients in case of emergencies. Here, we are focused to develop advance VTOL air ambulance which can be use in any condition and which are capable to carry out its work more precisely and efficiently.

Keywords VTOL, Healthcare facilities, Air Ambulance, Emergency.

1. Introduction

What comes to mind when you hear the word "air ambulance"? A transformer type vehicle or some awkward looking flying car although its fun to think about, in reality an air ambulance is most often either a fixed-wing aircraft or a helicopter. From the outside, apart from the markings that identify it as such, you would never know it to be different from any other aircraft. All planes and helicopters provide a valuable service to transport us from place to place. We usually need transportation for vacation or business travel needs, or even just for fun. When it comes to an air ambulance like Air Evac International, transportation is a lifesaver.

Electric vertical take-off and landing (eVTOL) aircraft are being constructed and tested, and they vary in configuration from hovercraft to electric fans. In 2010, Moore introduced the NASA Puffin VTOL electric tail sitter concept, highlighting the potential of electric propulsion to enable low-cost, quiet, and reliable short-range VTOLs. In the same year, Kroo founded ZeeAero, now Kitty Hawk, to build an eVTOL flying car. Since then, many researchers, companies and start-ups have started working on eVTOL. More than 130 electric VTOL concepts have been proposed, and venture

capitalists have invested more than \$1 billion in promising eVTOL start-ups. Moore and his colleagues worked on the idea of on-demand air mobility, hybrid eVTOLs, the advantages of electric propulsion compared to combustion and gas turbines, and the distributed electric propulsion of the X-57 Sceptor. Uber has hired both Moore and McDonald and is trying to build infrastructure for eVTOLs through its Uber Elevate program. Kitty Hawk, Lilium, Joby Aviation and E-Hang are four of the start-ups developing electric VTOLs. Kitty Hawk has developed and is currently testing two vehicles: the Cora, an elevator + excursion air taxi, and the Flyer, a hoverbike. Lilium is a German start-up building an eVTOL electric duct fan. They have flown many prototypes including a two-seat jet and are now developing a five-seat aero taxi. Joby Aviation has conducted electric propulsion tests and is building an eVTOL prototype. E-Hang is a Chinese quadrotor UAV company that has built and tested the E-Hang 184 personal drone with humans on board. This article seeks to understand which is the best eVTOL design, introducing and discussing all the different configurations, from the first developed in the 1950s and the 1960s to the present eVTOL configurations. At last, the performances of the three main eVTOL configurations are evaluated and compared using data from existing prototypes.

2. Methodology

Figure 1: Mission profile of VTOL

Figure 1 shows the mission profile of our aircraft. As its name implies, our aircraft take-off in vertical manner and until the stalling velocity reaches, it gets in hover and transition phase. After climbing to specific altitude, its starts cruising. An emergency site is also provided in mission profile which can be for two purposes, first it maybe to lift-up the patient from specific place or secondly in case of actual emergency so that an aircraft will land on specific place for safety. After this phase, the aircraft will again follow the same profile as mentioned.

3. Design

3.1 External design

The external design of our eVTOL is prepared in OpenVSP software as suggested by organizers. Figure 3,4,5,6 shows top view, front view, side view of our eVTOL aircraft. We have designed the opening or entry of aircraft from back side of vehicle from where we can enter. Talking about the software, this Particular software is used to create and produce the exterior design of the aircraft is OpenVSP also known as Open Vehicle Sketch Pad, it is an open-source parametric aircraft geometry tool originally developed by NASA. It can be used to create 3D models of aircraft and to support engineering analysis of those models.

It is very simple to use and is hence recommended for conceptual design making. It does not reflect the final product as the final product undergoes complex simulations in various software such as Ansys and Catia. The models made in OpenVSP show the ideation stage of the aircraft that is to be improved on.

Figure 2: Top view of our eVTOL aircraft

Figure 3: Top view of our eVTOL aircraft

Figure 4: Side view of our eVTOL aircraft

Figure 5: Front view of our eVTOL aircraft

3.2 Interior design

Figure 7 describe the interior design of the vehicle whose footprint is 3m×2m×1.5m. We can see in the figure that all the equipment is arranged according to the most efficient way as it could be according to us.

Figure 6: Interior design of our aircraft

3.3 CFD Analysis

Figure 7

Figure 8

Figure 9

4. Stability study

The stability characteristics of an aerial vehicle heavily depend on the design of each part of the overall design (e.g. main wing, fuselage, engine etc.), but more importantly on the empennage. The analysis can be broken down into the inherent response of the aerial vehicle to external disruptions of its equilibrium position, and its behavior when a control surface is deflected. In general, the two necessary conditions for a successful mission are the ability to achieve equilibrium flight and the capability to perform maneuvers for a wide range of flight velocities and altitudes. The fundamental parameters that determine the longitudinal stability in equation below with the condition for stable flight of the pitching moment coefficient at the center of gravity Cm_{cg} being zero.

$$Cm_{cg} = Cm_0 + Cm_{\alpha} \alpha + Cm_{\delta e} \delta e = 0$$

To meet the condition $Cm_{cg} = 0$ (trim condition) a deflection of the elevator is necessary, namely δe_{trim} given by equation

$$\delta e_{tri} = \frac{Cm_0 + Cm_{\alpha} a_{trim}}{Cm_{\delta e}}$$

With the trim angle of attack, a_{trim} being influenced also by the change of the aerial vehicle's lift coefficient due to elevator deflection. Similar analyses are made for lateral and directional stability.

5. Results and Calculation

5.1 Initial sizing of aircraft and configuration

5.1.1 Crew

Aircraft is carrying one patient and a paramedic. So, the crew capacity is **2**.

5.1.2 Length

The length of aircraft as **6.6 m**.

5.1.3 Height

The bottom to top distance of our aircraft is **2.9 m**.

5.1.4 Wingspan (b)

The wingspan of our designed aircraft is **11.8 m**

5.1.5 Root chord (C_r)

The root chord is the measurement from leading edge to trailing edge at the wing root. For our aircraft's wing, the root chord is **1.62 m**.

5.1.6 Tip chord (C_t)

The tip chord of our aircraft's wing is **1.18 m**.

5.1.7 Average chord

The average chord can be defined as –the sum of root chord and tip chord divide by two.
Mathematically,

$$\frac{C_r + C_t}{2} = 1.4$$

5.1.8 Wing area (S)

For a straight tapered-wing, the wing area can be calculated by multiplying the wingspan and the average chord.
Mathematically,

$$S = b \times \text{average chord} = 16.52 \text{ m}^2$$

5.1.9 Aspect ratio (AR)

Aspect ratio is a ratio of square of wingspan to wing area. Mathematically,

$$AR = \frac{b^2}{S} = 8.43$$

5.1.10 Taper ratio (t)

The ratio of tip chord to root chord is known as taper ratio which is given as-

$$t = \frac{c_t}{c_r} = 0.7284$$

5.1.11 Mean Aerodynamic Chord (MAC)

The mean aerodynamic chord is given by-

$$MAC = C_r \times \frac{2}{3} \times [(1+t+t^2) \div (1+t)] = 1.41 \text{ m}$$

5.2 Performance parameters of aircraft

5.2.1 Cruise speed our aircraft

There are various formula to find the velocity of aircraft. We are using the following formula to calculate the velocity is - 367.2 km/hr

5.2.2 Range

The range of an eVTOL aircraft can be calculated by the formula $R = V_{\infty} \times t = 204 \text{ km}$

5.3 Battery Selection

5.3.1 Battery used

For making our eVTOL aircraft, we used /.

5.3.2 Number of motors

A high-performance electric motor has to be used for vertical take-off and landing aircraft is used to give high performance. In our aircraft, we used 6 electric motors.

5.3.3 Propellers

Here 6 tilt—propellers are used where 4 propellers tilt vertically including entire motor nacelle and 2 propellers tilt vertically with a linkage mechanism. We have selected 5 propeller blades for our aircraft as it more efficient and the detail calculations are going to happen in stage 2 report.

5.3.4 Motor selection

According to our application, we have selected HPDM-250 motor.

5.4 Flight Time

The flight time is the pilot time that commences when an aircraft moves under its own power for the purpose of flight and ends when the aircraft comes to rest after landing. In our case, we have estimated the flight time as-

$$\text{Flight time} = \frac{\text{Battery capacity} \times \text{Battery discharge}}{\text{Average Amp draw} \times 60} = \frac{3687.5416 \times 2876.28}{49.16 \times 60 \times 60}$$

$$\therefore \text{Flight time} = 59.93 \text{ min}$$

5.5 Weight estimation

5.5.1 Crew weight

As per the problem statement given, our aircraft is autonomous it means that it doesn't require pilot to carry out flying operation. But another condition was given that an aircraft should carry one patient and a paramedic so there are 2 person on board and by considering the average weight of human weight, we are considering the total weight of crew on board as 170 kg.

5.5.2 Payload weight

As per the list of paramedic equipment given to us, the list of all equipments along with their weights are given in table 2

Table 2: Gross weight of equipments

Sr. No.	Name of equipment	Quantity	Gross Weight of equipment (Kg)
1.	Seats and Components	2	15
2.	Monitors	1	3
3.	Storage Wall	1	3
4.	Storage Cabinet	2	10
5.	Sink for washing	1	30
6.	Patient Stretcher	1	55
7.	Immobilization & Patient handling equipment	1	3
8.	Transport ventilator	1	5
9.	Portable Oxygen tank	3	150
10.	ECG system	1	3
11.	Diagnostic equipment	1	15
12.	Emergency bags & boxes	3	1
13.	Bleed control & trauma kit	5	15
14.	Burns kit	5	35
15.	Defibrillators	1	60
16.	Injection & Infusion Kits	5	0.5
			Total – 403.5

The gross weight of equipment is 403.5 kg. As mentioned early that crew weight is 170 kg so the final payload becomes-

$$M_{payload} = M_{equipments} + M_{crew}$$

$$\therefore M_{payload} = 403.5 + 170$$

$$\therefore M_{payload} = \mathbf{573.5 \text{ kg}}$$

5.2.3 MTOW estimation

As we know that the mass of battery is 376.6 kg and the empty mass of aircraft is 1419.4 kg whereas the mass of payload is calculated as sum of crew weight and weight of all medical equipment. The weight of crew is 170 kg and the weight of medical equipment is 403.5 kg so the total payload mass is 573.5 kg. Finally the maximum take-off weight (MTOW) is calculated by-

$$MTOW = M_{battery} + M_{payload} + OEW$$

Where,

OEW = Operating Empty Weight which after calculation was determine as 1419.4 kg.

$$\therefore MTOW = 376.6 + 573.5 + 1419.4$$

$$\therefore \mathbf{MTOW = 2369.5 \text{ kg}}$$

6. Conclusion

Under circumstances that require medical urgencies, where conventional means of transport are not applicable, a VTOL UAV is convenient as it falls under the mission requirements that help in the efficient transport of the patients under medical observation. In this report, we have prepared a conceptual design of eVTOL which is efficient be used as an air ambulance. Here we have used Lithium-nickel-cobalt-manganese-oxide battery which is more efficient according to our application. The battery is rechargeable which is going to be charged during the flight. Our eVTOL have 6 tilt-rotor propellers which help to take-off and also in horizontal flight. The range of this aircraft is 204 and the flight time is 59.93 min.

References

- [1] Seunghee Yu, Yongjin Kwon, —Development of VTOL Drone for Stable Transit Flightl Journal of Computer and Communication, 2017, 5, 36-43.
- [2] A thesis on , —Development of an efficient vertical takeoff and landing aircraft by Alexander Desiletsl, 2019.
- [3] Daeil Jo, Yongjin Kwon, —Analysis of VTOL UAV Propellant Technologyl Journal of Computer and Communication, 2017, 5, 76-82.
- [4] Rohit Goyal, Adam Cohen, —Advanced Air Mobility: Opportunities and Challenges Deploying eVTOLs for Air Ambulance Servicel Appl. Sci. 2022, 12, 1183.
- [5] Article on Bell Boeing V-22 Osprey on Wikipedia
- [6] Mark J. S. Lopez, Caitlin S. Duffy, Mark B. Tischler, Paul Ruckel, —Bell V-280 Hover Flight Dynamics Model Validation and Update with Flight Test Datal , Corpus ID: 250042522, 2021.
- [7] Haowei Gu, Ximin Lyu, Zexiang Li, Shaojie Shen, and Fu Zhang, —Development and Experimental Verification of a Hybrid Vertical Take-Off and Landing (VTOL) Unmanned Aerial Vehicle(UAV)l, Conference Paper · June 2017
- [8] Chris Stonor, —Orca Aerospace and NLR to jointly develop eVTOL air ambulancel, 2021.
- [9] Article on —Helicopter Emergency Medical Servicesl on Wikipedia
- [10] C Bliamis et al, —Aerodynamic and stability analysis of a VTOL flying wing UAVl, IOP Conference series: Materials Science and Engineering, 2020.
- [11] Xiao-Guang Yang et al, —Challenges and key requirements of batteries for electric vertical takeoff and landing aircraftl, Joule 5, 1644-1559, July 2021.
- [12] Dr. James Wang, —Weight and Performance Estimation for eVTOL aircraftl, 2022.
- [13] Priyank Pradeep and Peng Wei, —Energy-Efficient Arrival with RTA Constraint for Multirotor eVTOL in Urban Air Mobilityl, Journal of aerospace information systems, April 2019.
- [14] Priyank Pradeep, Gano B. Chatterji, et al, —Wind-Optimal Trajectories for Multirotor eVTOL Aircraft on UAM Misionl, Conference paper, June 2020.
- [15] Reg Austin, —Unmanned Aircraft Systemsl, reference book.
- [16] Noah Salvador Lopez, et al, —Preliminary Aerodynamic Analysis for the Multi-Disciplinary Design and Optimisation of a Long-range eVTOL Aircraftl, conference paper, Januaray 2022.
- [17] Bacchini, A.; Cestino, E. Key Aspects of Electric Vertical Take-off and Landing Conceptual Design. Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part GJ. Aerosp. Eng. 2020, 234, 774–787.
- [18] Bacchini, A.; Cestino, E.; Van Magill, B.; Verstraete, D. Impact of lift propeller drag on the performance of eVTOL lift+cruise aircraft. Aerosp. Sci. Technol. 2021, 109, 106429.
- [19] eVTOL Aircraft Directory, Electric VTOL News by the Vertical Flight Society. Available online: <https://evtol.news/aircraft> (accessed on 6 February 2021).
- [20] Kundu, A.K.; Price, M.A.; Riordan, D. Conceptual Aircraft Design: An Industrial Approach; Wiley: Hoboken, NJ, USA, 2019; p. 1056; ISBN 978-1-119-50028-5.
- [21] Pham, R.N. High Performance VTOL Convertiplanes. U.S. Patent No. 6,974,105, 13 December 2005.
- [22] Crawford, C.C.; Heiges, M.W.; Wasikowski, M. Analysis of Tiltwing Aircraft Configuration Potential. SAE Trans. 1996, 105, 1267–1280.
- [23] Taarabt, S.A.; Bernier, A.T.; Chen, Y.; Compere, H.; Dore, A.; Fransolet, M.; Jumpertz, R.D.; Macchiaiolo, L. Graduate Team Aircraft Design Competition: Electric Vertical Takeoff and Landing (E-VTOL) Aircraft Mistral Air Taxi Team Name: The Huggy’s Birds. 2019.
- [24] Cinar, G.; Cai, Y.; Chakraborty, I.; Mavris, D.N. Sizing and Optimization of Novel General Aviation Vehicles and Propulsion System Architectures. In Proceedings of the 2018 Aviation Technology, Integration, and Operations Conference, Atlanta, GA, USA, 25–29 June 2018; ISBN 978-1-62410-556-2.
- [25] Jeevanantham, V.; Vadivelu, P.; Manigandan, P. Material Based Structural Analysis of a Typical Landing Gear. IJSET 2017, 4, 2348–7968.
- [26] Aircraft Tire—Engineering Data.
- [27] Bachmann, J.; Yi, X.; Gong, H.; Martinez, X.; Bugeda, G.; Oller, S.; Tserpes, K.; Ramon, E.; Paris, C.; Moreira, P.; et al. Outlook on ecologically improved composites for aviation interior and secondary structures. CEASAeronaut. J.2018, 9, 533–543.

- [28] Yi, Y. Review and Future of Aircraft's Propulsion Type. J. Phys. Conf. Ser. 2019, 1345, 032075.
- [29] Jeevanantham, V.; Vadivelu, P.; Manigandan, P. Material Based Structural Analysis of a Typical Landing Gear. IJSET 2017, 4, 2348–7968.
- [30] Sanchez-Carmona, A.; Cuerno-Rejado, C. Vee-tail conceptual design criteria for commercial transport aeroplanes. Chin. J. Aeronaut. 2019, 32, 595–610.
- [31] Technology Roadmap to 2050. Available online: <https://www.iata.org/contentassets/8d19e716636a47c184e7221c77563c93/technology20roadmap20to20205020no20foreword.pdf>.

A Brief Author Biography

Yuvraj Pagare– Yuvraj Ramdas Pagare is a dedicated aerospace engineer and aspiring author from Nashik, Maharashtra, India. He holds a diploma in Mechanical Engineering and a degree in Aerospace Engineering from Sandip University, consistently excelling in his studies. During his academic tenure, Yuvraj interned at prestigious organizations such as HAL and DRDO, gaining valuable experience in aircraft components and systems.

Yuvraj has published five research papers and his first book, “The Success Attitude Matrix: Unravelling the Many Faces of Achievement.” He has worked on projects such as VTOL, rocket model design, UAV prototype development, and airfoil optimization. Yuvraj has also won various national and state-level competitions and attended three international conferences as a delegate.

With his strong background and technical skills, Yuvraj aims to inspire readers to unlock their full potential and achieve remarkable success.

Jaidev Reddy– Jaidev Reddy is currently pursuing a Bachelor of Technology in Aerospace Engineering at Sandip University, Nashik, India. With a strong interest in aerodynamics and design engineering, Jaidev has gained practical experience as an Aero Engineer in the R&D Department of Sky-Circuit Innovations, where he focuses on propeller efficiency analysis. He was awarded by HAL India for his insightful presentation on the integration of AI and the metaverse in the field of aviation and aerospace. Jaidev is dedicated to advancing his knowledge and expertise in aerospace engineering.

Manav Patel– Manav Patel is a dedicated aerospace engineer with a strong passion for designing and developing innovative solutions. He holds a Bachelor's degree in Aerospace Engineering from Sandip University & a Diploma in Mechanical Engineering. During his academic tenure, Manav interned at prestigious organizations such as HAL, AIESL, and DRDO, gaining valuable experience in design, development, and analysis of aircraft components and systems. Manav's technical skills include proficiency in CAD software (Catia, SolidWorks, AutoCAD), finite element analysis and simulation (Ansys), and strong understanding of structural analysis and design principles. He has worked on projects such as Rocket model design, UAV prototype development, and aircraft wing optimization. Manav is eager to pursue a career in the aerospace industry, contributing to the development of innovative and sustainable solutions. With his strong academic background, industrial experience, and technical skills, he is poised to make a significant impact in the industry.

Prathamesh Sapale– Prathamesh Sapale is currently pursuing his degree in Aerospace Engineering at Sandip University, Nashik. His passion lies in Aerodynamics, design, and system integration, supported by proficiency in software tools like Solidworks, Catia, and Mission Planner. He has gained valuable experience through multiple internships at renowned companies such as AIESL (AIR INDIA ENGINEERING SERVICES LIMITED), AIRBOTS AEROSPACE, and KIKSHIFT. Prathamesh is deeply committed to expanding his knowledge and skills within the dynamic field of Aerospace engineering.